

Translation Transformations and Its Description

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the issue of interpretation of translation transformations as a means of understanding the linguistic and cultural value of words and phraseological units. Different aspects of language units are analyzed and their specific features are explained. The article examines the interaction of translation transformations with other modifications. Also, the effect of complex translation transformations on expressing the discursive form of the original text in the translation is considered. The problem of multi-interpretation of back-translation, study of different aspects of inversion and its properties is studied. The article also discusses the principles of the relationship between conversion and other changes in translation. In addition, we analyze the effect of complex translation changes on the transmission of discursive forms of the original text.

Keywords: translation, converse translation, translational transformations, converse transformation, interpretation, discourse form of the text, variant and invariant aspects of translation.

INTRODUCTION

Translation transformation is one of the most actively studied phenomena in modern translation theory. However, this situation has not been resolved yet. It attracted attention because of the problem. In the literature addressing current issues in translation theory, there is discussion of the variability of oral translation types during translation transformation. Translators pay attention to grammatical, lexical, semantic, logical, and semantic features that serve as the basis for translation. This article is

devoted to studying the essence of this problem. Naturally, our task here is not to draw attention to the fact that the problem has a complex solution, but to shed light on the phenomenon of translational transformation during translation. When translating the semantic content of the original text into another language, the degree of influence of transformation is analyzed. To this end, we will study the principles of interpretation of this transformation based on its diversity: lexical-semantic (explicit), grammatical (morphological and structural-syntactic), semantic and discursive-expressive aspects.

METHODS

Within translation theory science, many translation scholars attach great importance to the study of transtranslation. [Komissarov V.N. 1973; Gorokhova A.I. 2004; Bruce E.V. 2007]. What is interesting about this phenomenon is that the nature of these translation corrections (changes) is very similar to the nature of antonym translations [Karabanova O.O. 2000; Garbovsky N.K. 2007]. When you use antonym translations and perform translation transformations, the grammatical and lexical levels of the language change simultaneously. At the same time, the nature of the transition takes on a deeper character, since lexical and grammatical substitutions and changes in the direction of action are also added to it. Usually, translation involves complex changes in translation, as they affect the semantic aspects of the text [Latyshev L. 1983, 317; Shechar A.D. 1988, 215]. In case of transformation, first of all, the semantic aspects of the situational image change. That is, the object of the sentence is described or described as if it were from the other side (other means of describing the same object are also used). . In this case, only the pragmatic semantic harmony (semantic direction) of the elements remains unchanged. In translation studies, A. Zholkovsky and I. Melchuk interpret transitional transformation as "a description of the same relationship on the other side..." [Steer E. 1970, 85].

Transformations are characterized by the semantic opposition of functions. In a convertible, logical components stand out. Moreover, in this case the various referential actions are opposed to each other. In linguistics, a transformation is considered a pair of words or phrases that express the same meaning from different angles. For example, "A has B = B belongs to A"; "A before B = B of A" [Latyshev L.K. 1983, 375]. Translation phenomena can occur within a language or during translation from one language to another. But now it is more important for us to analyze translation transformations in bilingual translations, so we will consider use cases in English-Uzbek and Russian-English translations. It can also be added that transformation is highly dependent on the outcome of the situation or communication depicted. In explicit (descriptive) expressions, the "new" (original) is based on a method of logical reasoning based on probability criteria through: Special appearance or other symbols. May contain active substances (not mentioned in text). The fact that an object is not displayed does not mean that it does not exist in the situation or communication process described. Implicit (input) objects can be the key to a clear and "appropriate" description of the context of the translation process.

Below we will consider an example of a situation where the conversion transformation is used. The analyzed translation transformations are highlighted in italics and numbered, sentence frames are underlined. An example:

(1). Deputy Prime Minister Ilya Klebanov, ³**in charge of** the military- industrial complex conceded during a preparatory trip to ⁶**New Delhi** ¹last week, that Russia's ⁸**stranglehold** on ⁷**Indian** contracts ⁹**was under threat**.

Translation

(1.) ¹*O,,tgan hafta* ²*Rossiya davlatidagi harbiy-sanoat kompleksiga* ³**rahbarlik qiluvchi** ⁴*Rossiya bosh vaziri o,,rinbosari I. Klebanov* ⁶**Hindistonga** tayyorgarlik tashrifi davomida Rossiyaning ⁷**Hindiston harbiy importidagi** ⁸**ustun mavqei** tahdid ostida ⁹**ekanligini** tan oldi

RESULTS

In order to preserve the rheme of the sentence in the translation and to avoid repeating the form of dividing it into actual parts in the translated language, it was necessary to deviate a little from the lexicogrammatical form of the sentence. ⁶(“New Delhi”) lexical unit⁶(“Hindiston”) is being replaced by the word: situation one description clearly follows from the other. The phrase "visited Delhi" can also be understood as meaning that he got acquainted with the attractions of the capital of India. In addition, the concretization method was also used (“Deputy Prime Minister” – ⁴Rossiya bosh vazirining o,,rinbosari”). ³(“In charge of”) lexical unit was translated instead of ³(“rahbarlik qiluvchi”). The addition method was also used: ²(“Rossiya davlatida”). The most important is a complex nominative substitution with an element of semantic convertibility was being translated: ⁸(“stranglehold”) ⁸(“ustun mavqe”). Here, the goal of avoiding ambiguity and confusion led to the obligation to use another transformation. ⁷(“on Indian contracts”) ⁷(“Hindiston harbiy importi”) was translated by replacing the element and added the word “harbiy”. This replacement can also be understood as a conversion phenomenon, depending on the picture of the situation. “shartnomalarsiz” “harbiy import” is almost certainly impossible. These two elements require each other. Another element was used to create a picture of the situation: a denotative "shift" along the referent was created. Because it is clear that the field of description is not limited to the element "contracts" and this situation, in our opinion, does not allow a complete description of the situation. Why this version of the translation is used can be explained by the fact that the strictness of the description of the situation is being slightly relaxed in the translated language. Because in this context it is not required to use a strict form. Here a step towards free translation is made. But the level of accusation of baseless speculation is not exceeded.

DISCUSSION

Using the used transformations, we tried to clearly express the meaning of the communicative center in the given sentence through direct translation ("was under threat"). If we had preserved the figurativeness of the word ("stranglehold") in the translation, then the meaning of the element ("was under threat") would have been required to be revised. If we were to translate these elements while preserving the figurativeness, we would get a sentence like ("strangling to death ... under threat"), which is not typical of Uzbek language methodology. It is possible to "get rid of" "suffocation", "get rid of" and even "get rid of it". If we had translated this word in the form of "suffocation", then in another part of the sentence, the description of the situation, conversion would have been formed. Comparing the contexts of different languages, we came to the conclusion that although it is very

difficult to break away from the linguistic means of expression inherent in the original text, sometimes it is necessary to use them.

As can be seen from the first example given, the translation used not only grammatical and lexical substitutions, changes and additions, but also two translation modifications that name the subject from a completely different perspective. suffocate, suffocate) — translated as (“highest position”). Another aspect worth noting is that the ending of the sentence could be translated using an antonym: (“Russia may lose its dominant position in Indian military imports”). The second example of analysis shows that it is impossible to repeat in a translation the discursive form (i.e. the division into actual parts) of the original text without changing the linguistic character of the original text. In the second example, the presence of syntactic variants is also important. The determiner is changed to possessive and a conversion transformation is performed. In the translation, the verb/part "yields" is replaced by the verb/part "can beat". As a result, this situation leads to the name of the movement coming from the other side.

CONCLUSION

The above example confirms that transformation transformations are complex. They are just grammatical, lexical and logical. It is incorrect to interpret this as change. As can be seen from the example, transformation transformation involves lexical, grammatical and logical changes simultaneously and affects all aspects of the linguistic form of a sentence. Unlike natural, purely grammatical transformations and antonymic translations, the level of influence of transformational transformations is more important in conveying the semantic content of the original text. These transformations are widely used in translation. Their use always requires movement to the rhetorical center of the sentence, the formation of a clear expression of the rhetorical center of the sentence and a direct transition. According to the analysis, the nature of translation transformation can be said to be complex and complicated.

The complex nature of the transformations performed during the translation process is based on features such as lexical-semantic, grammatical, semantic, logical, and discourse-expressive. The more ways a translation can fully interpret the content of the original text, the greater the importance of the translation transformation. The richness of linguistic features in the source text increases the need to use transformations in translation. In particular, the deeper the meaning of linguistic units within a sentence, the more features of transformation there are. If there are multiple interpretations, the same transformation may be interpreted in different ways. The number of interpretations corresponds to the variant form of the translation.

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